

A Study on Artificial Intelligence in Banking Innovation” - Indian Banking Tomorrow with Today’s Thought...

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Abstract

In the world of Artificial Intelligence (AI), banking has not limited itself to fewer banker operations but has evolved itself to the changes surrounding the ease of doing Banking Business. From complicated paper works to digitization of records within second with the help of ATM, Cash Deposit Machine(CDM), Passbook machine, Card less transactions, Fingerprint Banking Mobile banking, E-banking and Internet banking etc...Enabling faster Transaction and transparency at high level. Thus offers a number of perceptions on what we see today and how did we get here? What is currently significant? And what might be the future of banking Industry? This paper investigates the new age banking with the progressive innovation of artificial intelligence in banking sector as challenges and opportunity, labor forces replaced by robotics and AI potential to impact the Banking sector. The researchers try to study the impact of AI with the help of Banks which have already developed AI system in their operational management through Secondary data i.e. Journals, Research papers, Articles, Case studies and publications cited from the year 2015 to 2017. To analyze such a large number of scripts, text mining technique is used and also using a dictionary of terms belonging to both banking and business intelligence domains.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence (AI), Banking Business.

Introduction

Technology as a driving tool has increased the efficiency of business with the concept of Earth as Global Village for operations. The rapid growth of science and technology has largely had its effect in the field of Healthcare, Manufacturing, Customer service, Finance and Banking sectors. Factors such as managing huge data from ever growing population, transaction across globe are few driving forces to adopt AI in business. While AI has made ways to overcome conventional way of doing business in the above sectors. Banking with AI has proven to be time saving by 60% and efficient by 100%, that’s a win-win Situation to both banker and its customer proving them to change the dimensions of handling business. Assistance to do more with little - From the manual entries to the digital accounts, From money transfers to SWIFT.

Artificial Intelligence (AI)

In concept, Artificial Intelligence (AI) has been around from 1950's, ever since John McCarthy defined it as "the science and engineering of making intelligent machines". It has evolved itself from simple Chess games to the Voice assistance model today in Cellular phone. Today, there is widespread application of AI as the hottest trends for 21st Century. Ever since its innovation it has been a debatable topic on –"Can Computers think, act, react, and respond to certain inputs - While less debates on what AI actually means". That is because the application of AI is widespread from Simplest of Cellular phone voice assistance (Apple Siri, Google Now) to the Experiments of Driverless cars or the Restaurants run by Robotics fall under single Umbrella. This point of view on Banking Business refers to Artificial Intelligence is an area of computer science that replaces the use of mankind by computer programming software which can enables to perform functions of human, think and respond back.

Ex: AI in assisting the ATM operations.

Banking Business

Time with trade has changed the system of dealing with business while barter system replaced by trading with gold coins and further replaced with Currency. The trading with most popular currencies across globe lead to the requirement of efficient banking system. Banking is a financial undertaking dealing with Borrowing and lending functions at large, products like saving bank account, loans, and credit offerings are very common in nature. The operation of banking has evolved to the need of the present day with commercial banking operations and investment banking activities dealings with businesses. Development of special banking software and customized banking has grown along science and technology. Banks are often referred as the backbone of the economic development of the country. Banking sector in India has a potential growth and is expected to be the 5th banking Industry in the world by 2020 and 3rd largest by 2025. The banking Industry is currently worth Rs. 81 trillion (US \$ 1.31 Trillion) with 26 public sector, 20 public sector bank, 43 foreign banks along with 61 regional banks and more than 90000 credit Cooperative banks.

Objectives

- To study the concept of AI and driving factors for adoption in Banking.
- To study the impact of AI in banking sector.
- To Understand AI as challenges and Opportunities in Banking

Review of literature

1. Meryem Duygun Fethi and Fotios Pasiouras, in their paper Titled "Assessing Bank efficiency and performance with operational research and artificial intelligence technique: A Survey". This paper gives a comprehensive study of 196 data observation which comprises O.R (operational Research) and AI (artificial Intelligence) which assess banking performance. It also speaks about credit worthiness and underperformance in bank. It also talks on techniques such as Neural Network and support vector machines.

2. Ankith Kesharwani Shailendar Singh Bisht

"The impact of Trust and perceived risk on internet banking adoption in India: An extension of technology acceptance model" it aims at understanding the technology acceptance model in relationship with net banking in India. It gives an insight about behavior intention of net banking negative impact on perceived risk

3. Avneet Pannu, Paper Titled “Artificial Intelligence and its Applications in Different Areas” it explores opportunities in empowering AI, the growth of artificial intelligence in last decades in various sectors with the overview of technology in application of business sector and service industry

Limitation

- Lack of time frame study.
- AI is a multidisciplinary study while this paper is only limited to Banking sector.
- Restricted to limited Geographic study (Indian Banking system).

Research Methodology

The researchers try to study the through Secondary data i.e. Journals, Research papers, Articles, Case studies and publications cited from the year 2015 to 2017. To analyses such a large number of scripts, text mining technique is used and also using a dictionary of terms belonging to both banking and business intelligence domains. Descriptive and Conceptual research method is adopted for the study.

1. Factors Influencing AI in Banking Sector In India

Low Processing Time

AI will illuminate major time taken for processing a particular transaction in a given time with low human intervention 60 % less time consumption and 100% accuracy.

Case Study

SBI has adopted an AI called Payjio, developed by SIA a technological based startup in Bengaluru. According to the study Payjo has responded to Million Queries from People across the Country accounting to 10000 enquiries per second or 864 million in a day. This is 25% of data managed by Google every day.

Progressive Banking

It helps the customer in answering to their regular Queries with lesser TAT (Turnaround Time) and increased efficiency.

Case Study

The AI developed By ICICI Bank help customer resolve FAQ, which are simple structured frameworks developed through responses received from customers. Bot, the AI software gives the correct response and it learns along the way saving the executor’s time by 40%.

Conveserational Banking

Introduction of AI which can respond back to the task performed or assist the customer in carrying out their banking operations has evolved with time making way to Conveserational banking at a large.

Ex: Voice Assistance, support by AI in Banking operations.

Case Study

With the launch of “EVA” the AI system in Axis Bank has enabled the bank to develop Conversational banking app helping consumer with both financial and non-financial products, Answers to FAQ, processing of Loan and other products. Currently the app is available on FB and Axis bank Web Page.

24/7 Banking

Machines the tired less inventions of the human era with unmatched efficiency and time taken to perform have always been proven right. The ability to function round the clock has drawn AI as future in Banking Arena.

Case Study

To help service the customers round the clock, Axis bank has implemented AI across 125+ Process across the country. Robotic Process Automation (RPA) is complete for most process, which includes support in financial segment as well i.e. loan disbursement, bulk process and ATM Support along with Voice assistance.

Security (Fraud Detection)

While Banks deal with money, safety and security is given a top priority by both the banker and its customer. AI currently is introduced in financial services as a fraud detector such as fake cards in operation, improved machine learning and big data to be managed via AI. It also enables fake call dedication and more.

Banking Technology

The rapid growth of science and technology enabling next level banking with AI has improved machine level learning and improved customer satisfaction, especially in customized banking with great back office data management efficiency. The Previous year Banking in India has seen adoption of AI for conversational banking, automation of underwriters in financial products, web and device with fingerprint process, paperless banking etc...

Case Study

DCB bank becomes the First Indian Bank to adopt Aadhaar based banking; it launched its operation in April 2016 followed by SBI, IDFC and others with the influence of AI.

Better Computing Power

Introduction of machine, replacing manpower at large has been effective in managing data at various ends and been proven to be efficient in managing time by 100 %.

Case Study

HDFC with the launch of EVA, the AI software the customer can obtain information about its products and services on real time basis. It removes the need of searching of data or obtaining such data through call. EVA will also help in handling real banking transaction. It will also complement upcoming digital platforms in exploring Digital Banking.

Cost Optimization

The element of profit is not just sales but also through cost minimization. AI in the areas of Unified Payment Interface (UPI) has leveraged the growing presence of banking through online platform such as M-Banking, I-Banking and more. Reducing the cost of Infrastructure for Financial Institutions.

Case Study

With the raise in smartphone users, mobile banking and e-wallets it is expected that smartphone user base to expand from 150+ million users currently to 500 million users by 2020, Introduction of products such as RuPay Cards by National Payment Corporation Of India (NPCI) which will allow real time money settlement for convenient experience of the customer, it is a foundation for Digital movement in India.

2. To study the impact of AI in banking sector

Customer Service

While customer service is the key to long term profitability and sustainability, the dynamic market has enabled customer with various choice making in choosing related products by different bankers while banks are adopting innovative systems such as AI to perform their regular banking activities attracting customer retention at large.

Observation

The introduction of AI in machine learning helps in new features to the customer such as how to perform a certain task, How to reset ATM pin, which is advanced with banking.

E-KYC and onboarding (Robotic Process Automation)

The RBI has legalized Aadhaar based banking which enables the banker to assess his/her account through biometric authentication, opening of banking accounts through e-KYC and banking Correspondent (BC) location. It is noted that time spent on SB accounts and Current account opening has reduced by 90% and 92% respectively.

Case Study

IDFC bank has become the first bank to Launch Biometric-Based payment through Aadhaar Pay, it aims at providing onboarding between 50,000-75,000 merchant to the enroll with 1,00,000 as target in 3 years.

Risk, Credit and credit rate scoring

Risk is the element of uncertainty involving multiple obligations at different levels such as operational risk, credit risk, market risk, business risk, liquidity risk etc... To negotiate such risk AI has become more efficient in understanding current banking needs and to mitigate risk.

Case Study

Axis bank with adoption of AI has developed Robust credit Risk model, evident from the fact that 80% of the suspicious transaction are free. 5% customers are identified as High risk by the introduction of AI-enabled neural network.

Real time Feedback from customers

SBI with the help of its AI Powered smart cameras that can capture facial expressions of a customer to understand the satisfactory level of Customers to offer a real time feedback on the usage.

3. To Understand AI as challenges and Opportunities in Banking

Digitalization of Banks

With the Effect of Govt. policies such as Digital India, Startup India, Jan Dhan Yojana and Aadhaar Card as mandate promoting digital banking system in India AI has a greater role to play as Digital alternatives. While the ROI in India for FinTech Project is 29% the highest in the Global Economy with 20% as Global Standards.

E-payment gateway

While Digital payment sector in India is growing and estimated to grow with the need and the emergence of Mobile payment solution and E-Wallets and P2P transfers, POS, One stop-shop solutions it becomes both challenge and opportunity for banker.

User Adoption (Employees)

With the effect of Machine Learning influenced by AI, which will replace huge manpower Resources with Machine Learning and programming at large. This is a potential threat to the employees of the organization.

User Adoption (Customers)

India is a Rural based country with 70% population living in villages, while 30% live in Urban settlements. Beside the population division, illiteracy, lack of access to banking, traditional way of saving money in homes, diversified geographical location are the major challenges for banking.

Finding and Suggestions

- Adaptation of AI with lack of Human Touch is a barrier in the Indian Banking sector.
- It is estimated that 80% of economic transactions in India still happen through cash, as

opposed to around 21% for developed economies

- AI in Banking sector stands in 8th position due to lack of maturity
- AI in banking to increase in next 12 months.

Conclusion

While India is still a Developing Economy, Adoption of technology such AI in Banking does not wait for maturity for its adoption. The raise in population makes ways to huge data and data management without the adoption of AI will be costly, time consuming and less efficient. AI has to sail a long way in banking to reach out its large audience in diversified country like India. Factors such as strong Govt Policies, growing business environment and rapid growth of science and technology will make ways to adopt of AI in Business sectors.

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The Changing Face of Marketing: Role of Artificial Intelligence in Shaping Consumer Experience

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Abstract

The human existence has been shaped by numerous discoveries that have benefited and at times even challenged the human race. Humans have excelled in creating things that have challenged its own imagination and hence justified the title of being the most intelligent species. History is testimony to the ways Steam Power, Electricity and Information Technology has impacted the human kind. The next revolution that is taking place, silently but at a rapid pace, is Artificial Intelligence (AI). The late physicist Stephen Hawking said that the success in the field of AI will perhaps be the biggest achievement of the human mind, but also warned of the possibility of the termination of the human race if we lose control.

There are many who believe that the human race will keep control over AI for many years to come and can reap significant benefits from the use of it. There are also significant others who are skeptical about the coexistence of the creator and its creation. Irrespective of the opposite schools of thought, AI has already started making significant impact on various aspects of life and is on its way to perhaps become the biggest disruption. We have witnessed so far. The aim of this paper is to trace the evolution of AI and look at the ways it's impacting the field of Marketing. The authors look to present a layman's understanding about AI's role in marketing and perhaps throw light on its probable future applications without inclining towards any particular school of thought.

Keywords: AI, Evolution, Technology, Marketing, Consumer Engagement, Experience

Introduction

What is Artificial Intelligence?

Artificial can refer to anything that is not real; it is something that's fake because it is simulated essentially. Intelligence however is a more complex term. It can be things such as logic, understanding, problem solving, creativity, etc. We call humans intelligent because they exhibit the traits mentioned and we can say the same about plants and animals. Now machines, computers, and robots are said to have “Artificial” intelligence as they mimic or simulate the